

Fig. S1. Pictures of pollen germination and growth *in vitro* between wild type and transgenic lines after 4 h and 6 h incubation. Scale bar: 100 μ m.

Fig. S2. Phenotypic observation of wild-type and transgenic maize at flowering stage.

Scale bar: 10 cm.

Table S1. PCR primers used in this study.

Primer name	Primer sequence (5'-3')	Usage
sgRNA-T1-F	cagt ggtctca GGCA CCTCGATGTGCTCAATGTTG	Synthesis of sgRNA
sgRNA-T1-R	cagt ggtctca AAACCAACATTGAGCACATCGAGG	
sgRNA-T2-F	cagt ggtctca GCCG TGCTGCAGCCTCATAATGC	
sgRNA-T2-R	cagt ggtctca AAAC GCATTATGAGGCTGCAGCA	
sgRNA-T3-F	cagt ggtctca TGTGCGGTGGTGACAGGCTGATGA	
sgRNA-T3-R	cagt ggtctca AAACTCATCAGCCTGTCACCACCG	
psgA-T1	GACCATAGCACAAGACAGGCGT	Detection of intermediate vectors
psgB-T2	CGAATGAGCCCTGAAGTCTGAAC	
psgC-T3	CATTTCAATTACCTCTTTCTCC	
pOSCas9-ZmCP03-F	GATGGGTTTTTATGATTAGAGTCC	Detection of expression vectors
pOSCas9-ZmCP03-R	GGCTCGTATGTTGTGTGG	